

LIGNIN SPINNING AND CARBONIZATION TO Nano-LAYERED GRAPHITIC STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Graphitic lignin-based nanocarbons were prepared from spun lignin/PVA nanofiber networks using dry pyrolysis (DP) at 900 °C and hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) at 200 °C under a pressure of ~200 psi. The graphite formations were confirmed in both DP and HTC treated samples using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). The electrical conductivity of DP treated samples was improved by 14 % compared to the HTC treated samples, showing that DP converts lignin into more conductive graphite components. The photoluminescence of both charring methods showed similar patterns, with the highest emission at 320 nm. The DP samples had two times higher intensity than the HTC samples and were red-shifted, while the HTC samples showed more broad peaks. Corroborating with Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) results, functional groups from lignin residue were present in the HTC samples, while they were attenuated in the DP samples. The most important finding of this study is that spun LignoBoost lignin/PVA fibers prepared *via* two different charring methods yield layered graphitic materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbonized lignin with a graphitic structure is an excellent material for various end uses due to its enhanced electrical, thermal, and mechanical properties. Lignin can be efficiently obtained from black liquor *via* the process of LignoBoost: this process cuts down the vigorous acid use in lignin isolation and applies improved dispersion methods, yielding a cost-effective and high-quality lignin. The resulting lignin possesses a low ash content and high energy density [1].

Thermal conversion of lignin into graphitic structure is a one-step synthetic procedure for layered graphite preparation. The thermochemical conversion of lignin begins at 130 °C where the lignin starts softening, while the actual decomposition takes place between 250 and 600 °C [2]. This range of temperatures occurs due to the thermal response of different atoms on the lignin molecule. Comparing the wood constituents of hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin, it is assumed that in the latter case carbon structure changes into onion-like allotropic nanophase during carbonization. This is due to lignin molecules' three-dimensional arrangement compared to, for example, the cellulose crystalline region. The onion-like spherical concentric fringes are graphitic structures and in prior studies have been observed in different sizes. The morphology of graphitized carbons usually features polygonization [3].

In dry pyrolysis (DP), the charring process takes place in controlled temperature conditions under inert atmosphere and the graphitic structure formation of biomass begins at ~700 °C [4]. The intensity of graphitic structure increases as the thermal processing temperature and treatment duration increase. The biomass graphitic structure could be achieved through the high-temperature thermal conversion of dry pyrolysis and/or *via* the relatively low temperature hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) treatment. The HTC thermo-chemically converts biomass into carbonaceous material under controlled

temperatures ranging from 180–220 °C [5], and the biomass potentially forms graphitic structures in these temperature ranges and under high pressure. The pressure influences shear stress within pores and promotes graphite production [11]. The advantages of the HTC treatment are: (i) the feasibility of forming graphitic structures at a relatively lower energy level; and (ii) the ability to char biomass in the presence of water. Water is the major component in the biomass and it is generally challenging to char in the presence of water. Thus this process is also beneficial in the context of charring other wet samples, for example, municipal sewage. However, charring the biomass using HTC may not convert sufficient sample into graphitic structure as compared to DP.

In this study, DP and HTC methods were used and compared for their graphite formation efficacy. The DP samples were processed at 900 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere, while HTC was performed at 180–200 °C under pressure in the presence of water. The carbonized lignin samples' electrochemical, optical, and structural differences were also investigated.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Electrospinning process

The LignoBoost lignin was first dissolved in 2 wt% NaOH aqueous solution to make a solution containing 20 wt% lignin. 20 wt% Poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) aqueous solution was then added such that the lignin/PVA weight ratio in the final mixture was 75/25. Electrospinning of the lignin/PVA solution was carried out in a Fluidnatek LE-10 electrospinning apparatus (Bioinicia SL, Spain) and two different spinning settings were applied to produce two samples: Sample A was processed under a voltage of 16.6 kV and a feeding rate of 0.5 mL/h, while Sample B was processed with a voltage of 21 kV and a feeding rate of 0.62 mL/h. The distance between the tip of the spinning capillary and the collector was 20 cm for both samples.

2.2 Charring conditions

Samples A and B were charred using dry pyrolysis (DP) under inert atmosphere (N₂) using a laboratory-scale GSL-1100X programmable tube furnace. The temperature was raised at a rate of 30 °C/min to a final temperature of 900 °C and held for an hour following the method from Gezahegn et al., 2019 [4].

Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) was carried out using a 600 mL Parr reactor (4760 series non-stirred pressure vessel). Distilled water was added to reach 5 % (w/v) of solid content. The samples were placed in a perforated cage and the reaction maintained for 6 h at 200 °C under ~ 200 psi. [6] After carbonization, samples were allowed to cool to below 100 °C prior to removal from the reactor.

2.3 Characterization of charred materials

2.3.1 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Nano-layered graphitic structures of the samples were observed using a Talos L 120C transmission electron microscope (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) operated at 120 kV. Samples were exfoliated using 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) solvent, [7] sonicated at 40 kHz for 30 min, and the supernatant then placed on a copper grid prior to analysis. The layered graphitic structures of Samples A and B from pyrolysis treatment are shown in Fig. 1.

2.3.2 Electrical conductivity (EC)

Electrical conductivity of the carbonized samples was measured using an Everbeing Int'l Corp. Four Point Probe coupled to a Keithly 2450 source meter (Tektronix). Prior to conductivity measurements, the carbonized samples were made into thin films by imbedding them into the polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) in order to ease the conductivity measurement with the four-point probe. The film was made in deionized water at 70 °C. Then the differences among the pure PVA, uncharred and charred spun lignin samples EC were compared.

2.3.3 Photoluminescence properties

The photoluminescence (PL) emission of the carbonized samples was obtained using a PerkinElmer LS-55 Fluorescence Spectrometer with slits set at 5 nm. The emission of each sample was less than 1 % compared to the standard of quinine sulfate in a 1 N sulfuric acid solution and showed Stokes shift.

2.3.4 Surface functional groups

Fourier-Transform Infrared–Attenuated Total Reflectance (FTIR-ATR) spectra were acquired using a Bruker spectrometer model Tensor 27 within a spectrum range of 4000 to 500 cm^{-1} , with 50 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Samples of A and B were analyzed before and after DP and HTC treatment.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Graphitic structure identification and functional groups

TEM revealed that both the DP and HTC charring processes produced layered nano-graphite based products. Graphitic lattices were visible after they were scratched with the NMP solvent (Fig. 1a and b) from the bright field and corresponding selected area electron diffraction (SAED). This result was also observed in previous studies [4, 8]. Differences in lattice arrangement were evident among the TEM images of the DP and HTC treated samples; a more diffuse ring pattern was visible in the HTC sample's SAED image. This diffuse ring could arise from amorphous carbon presence. Also in the case of DP, some onion-like graphite arrangement was observed at the edge of the sample, which was consistent with an earlier study (Fig. 1b) [3]. The graphitic lattice evidenced in the HTC TEM image was more disordered (Fig. 1c and d), suggesting the presence of disordered graphite due to the presence of a higher C/O and C/H ratio as compared to the DP treated sample.

In the HTC process, the sample is submerged in water and heated where the water is at subcritical condition ($< 374.15\text{ }^\circ\text{C} / 221.2\text{ bars}$). The first HTC reaction is observed above $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the temperature range of $180\text{--}250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is a practical implementation of HTC [9]. In both DP and HTC, hydrolysis, dehydration, condensation polymerization, decarboxylation, and aromatization are common reaction mechanisms, and lignin is observed to decompose between $180\text{--}200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the HTC process [5]. Therefore, the temperature was appropriate to the current HTC method. However, incomplete carbonization was observed under optical microscopy in the HTC sample (Fig. 2). Further, a reason for the incomplete carbonization of the HTC sample may also be the feedstock physical size: typically, the sample is shredded in order to mix well with water, [9] whereas in this case it was not.

In terms of FTIR, the most pronounced differences between the DP and HTC treated samples were the absence of a series of peaks in DP. For example, peaks between $1000\text{ and }1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ inherited from the starting material, C-O stretching vibrations of alkoxy or epoxy at 1052 cm^{-1} , and an accentuated broad peak at 3400 cm^{-1} resulting from O-H vibration in the HTC samples were attenuated or minimized in the DP samples. The $1570\text{ and }1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ peaks in the DP samples result from C=C bond stretching, indicating the presence of sp^2 hybridized carbons, and demonstrate the higher graphitic domain in the DP samples. The peaks at 1011 cm^{-1} result from C=O vibration, and at 1365 cm^{-1} from C=O symmetric bonds arising from carboxyl groups, while the 1700 cm^{-1} peak indicates the presence of carbonyl C=O groups. The $2700\text{ and }2760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ peaks result from the C-H vibrations of aromatic aldehyde, while the $2870\text{ and }2930\text{ cm}^{-1}$ peaks are due to the stretching vibration of CH and CH_2 , respectively, and the latter are less visible in the DP samples (Fig. 3).

3.2 Electrical properties

The electrical conductivity of the charred lignin materials [both with DP (A and B) and HTC (A and B)] is presented in Table 1 to compare the two charring methods.

The electrical conductivity of all charred lignin materials was higher than that of the neat PVA (that was used as a substrate in the form of a thin film to measure the EC) and of the uncharred lignin – both were not electrically conductive. The electrical conductivity of dry pyrolysis A (DP, A) was two times

higher compared to that of hydrothermal A (HTC, A), while both (DP, B) and (HTC, B) showed similar electrical conductivity of 4.3×10^{-3} S/m. The lowered EC from the HTC could result from incomplete conversion of the lignin starting material, as it was evident (as seen in Fig. 2) that this could impede the flow of electrical conductivity among the neighbouring sp^2 carbon atoms.

3.3 Emission properties

Graphitic samples treated with different carbonization methods could have shown different photoluminescence ranges of colors due to the presence of sp^2 and sp^3 hybridized carbons and their proportion and arrangement. However, DP and HTC treated samples demonstrated similar emission patterns with the presence of two peaks when treated with the same excitation wavelengths, showing the presence of two fluorescent components. The 320 nm excitation wavelength was the highest emission for all samples (Fig. 4). The HTC treated samples appeared broader and blue shifted compared to the DP samples, with the exception of sample (HTC, B), which was slightly red shifted. The blue photoluminescence occurs due to the quantum confinement of the graphene sp^2 carbons' electrons within the pi conjugation, and as well the appearance of zigzag edges [10]. The greater the abundance of sp^2 carbons, the larger the pi conjugation and the more red shifted the emission. This indicates that the DP method produced more sp^2 carbons as compared to the HTC process.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Both DP and HTC treatment resulted in conversion of lignin into a graphitic structure. The advantage of HTC carbonization is that, unlike DP, this process does not require sample drying prior to carbonization. However, the HTC process demonstrated a partially incomplete conversion of carbonaceous starting material, whereas the DP samples were completely carbonized. As a result, the DP treated lignin had the highest electrical conductivity and a higher photoluminescence, evidencing greater graphitic component presence. It was also evident from the TEM imaging that the appearance of the layered graphitic components was more irregular in the HTC as compared to the DP treated samples.

5 FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1: TEM images of samples treated with dry pyrolysis (DP) (a–b) and hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) (c–d).

Figure 2: Optical microscopy image of incomplete charring of hydrothermally treated lignin sample.

Figure 3: FTIR spectroscopy of samples treated with dry pyrolysis (DP) and hydrothermal carbonization (HTC). (“A” and “B” denote the lignin spinning preparation method.)

Figure 4: Photoluminescence images of samples treated with dry pyrolysis (DP) (a–b) and hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) (c–d). (“A” and “B” denote the lignin spinning preparation method.)

Sample ID	EC (S/m)
DP, A	8.0×10^{-3}
DP, B	4.3×10^{-3}
HTC, A	1.1×10^{-3}
HTC, B	4.3×10^{-3}

Table 1: Electrical conductivity of samples treated with dry pyrolysis (DP) and hydrothermal carbonization (HTC). (“A” and “B” denote the lignin spinning preparation method.)

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